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PIANO STRATEGICO
DELLA **PAC**
IL FUTURO DELL'AGRICOLTURA SOSTENIBILE

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1.1

Summary of the Activity

The workshop "Weaving data and territory" – the 2025 edition of the Forum LEADER Giovani organised by Rete PAC - Rete LEADER, GAL Elimos, and Liminal between October 6 and 30 – was an applied training and territorial service initiative. Organized as part of the LEADER¹ program, the workshop involved young participants in an intensive course focused on mapping, territorial analysis, and strategic communication. The activity was structured in two integrated modules: the collection and analysis of territorial data (Module A) and its translation into place-based communication strategies (Module B), culminating in a public presentation during the Forum LEADER 2025 conference.² This module focuses on the results and methods of Module A, through which Liminal representatives shared with participants methods already tested in other territorial regeneration contexts and exposed them to their Challenge method to local development processes.

During the workshop, the 38 participants—all under 35 and from 17 different regions of the country—rapidly moved from theory to practice, acquiring operational skills in reading the territory, strategic planning, and the use of digital communication as a tool for activating identified territorial strategies. The work generated 281 mapped Points of Interest, 41 interviews with local stakeholders, and four SWOT analyses, editorial plans, and sample digital communication content that can be used by the municipalities involved. The outputs were disseminated at the end of the activity, with the public sharing of data on Google Maps and the presentation of the strategic and communication projects developed at the Forum LEADER 2025 conference.

The ex-post evaluation, conducted according to an adaptation of the Kirkpatrick model,³ highlighted overall satisfaction and a high recommendation rate. The main value that emerged was collaboration and networking. Participants reported greater motivation, confidence, and clarity in their roles, identifying territorial analysis and communication as the most useful areas. The experience demonstrated the value of a format that combines learning, service, and impact for the host territories, indicating a possible evolution of the Forum LEADER Giovani into a continuing education

¹ LEADER is a European Union program that supports the development of rural areas through a "bottom-up" approach, in which the territories themselves decide on priorities and projects to be implemented. LAGs (Local Action Groups) are public-private partnerships that manage LEADER funds locally: they develop a territorial strategy, publish calls for proposals, select projects, and support beneficiaries, acting as a local control room.

² The Forum LEADER is an annual national meeting of Italian LAGs, dedicated to the exchange of practices and coordination on local development strategies. Active since 2022, the Forum LEADER Giovani is a workshop dedicated to young people interested in the LEADER program that accompanies the national meeting.

³ Kirkpatrick, Donald L. *Evaluating Training Programs: The Four Levels*. San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler, 1994.

format rather than an introductory workshop, designed to consolidate a community of young territorial planners around the LAG network over time.

2.1

Objective, Context, and Partners

The Forum LEADER Giovani is a training initiative on European Union policies and projects for local rural development, within the framework of the CAP Network Program - LEADER Network.⁴ The 2025 edition was conceived not only as a training event, but also as an opportunity to experiment with a methodology capable of providing a concrete service to the host territories and allowing participants to engage in applied learning.

The activity was the result of a co-design process involving various actors, each with specific but converging priorities. Liminal brought its conviction that working on territorial legibility is a fundamental lever in fragile rural contexts and proposed to expose participants to field mapping and analysis methods capable of making this lever's potential tangible. GAL Elimos emphasized the importance of this work taking place directly in the municipalities of its territory, while at the same time highlighting one of its strengths: place-based territorial marketing as a tool for giving visibility to local projects and resources. The Rete Nazionale PAC - Rete LEADER, on the other hand, highlighted the role of the Forum LEADER Giovani as a space where not only European policies are explored in depth, but concrete strategies are produced that can inspire the work of LAGs. Finally, GAL Castelli Romani and Monti Prenestini contributed to defining the objectives of the workshop, sharing its experience gained in activities with Liminal and offering a targeted assessment of the elements of previous collaborations that proved most effective in achieving LEADER programming objectives in the Monti Prenestini area. This discussion gave rise to the overall scope of the workshop: mapping and making the territory legible, critically analyzing the dynamics, developing initial project hypotheses, and translating them into *place-based* communication strategies to be shared with the network of Italian LAGs in the context of the Forum LEADER 2025.

At an operative level, Rete Nazionale PAC - Rete LEADER organized the training program, coordinated the work, and also took care of the logistics for the participants in the field. GAL Elimos hosted the initiative in the territory and, with the contribution of Prof. Maurilio Caracci, led the module focused on translating the analyses into communication strategies and content. Liminal participated by bringing its Challenge methodology to this intensive training context, focusing on place-based data collection and strategic analysis of the territory. Finally, GAL Metropoli Est, the organizing body of the 2025 edition

⁴ The Rete Nazionale PAC - Rete LEADER Program is a national initiative that supports the implementation of the LEADER/CLLD method within the Common Agricultural Policy, providing technical assistance, coordination, and support tools to LAGs and the administrations involved.

of Forum LEADER, provided the platform for the final presentation and dissemination of results.

3.1

Methodological Approach

The workshop was designed with a dual purpose: to offer participants an applied training experience and, at the same time, to produce a concrete service for the host territories. This choice stems from the way Liminal views fragile rural contexts: as complex systems in which traditional methods struggle to work because they either remain too abstract (top-down approaches) or fail to translate beyond participatory processes into structured actions (bottom-up approaches).

The initial theoretical component of the workshop made this diagnosis explicit, introducing the concepts of territorial fragility, complex systems, and the "double bind" between top-down policies and bottom-up initiatives. Before moving on to the operational phase, participants were presented with the Challenge methodology developed by Liminal as a concrete way of translating this theoretical reading into a practical approach: a format that combines fieldwork, strategic synthesis, and rapid feedback in a real territory. The workshop was designed as a training version of the Challenge, offering participants not only conceptual categories but also a coherent method for action, moving from observation to feedback in a very short time frame.

From a methodological and pedagogical point of view, Module A was divided into four closely related steps. The first was a close reading of the territory, through the mapping of Points of Interest (POI)⁵ and bilateral interviews with local stakeholders: seeing places in a structured way, listening to the stakeholders who represent the territory, and systematically documenting what normally remains as implicit knowledge. The second step consisted of immediately transforming this reading into an initial operational output, organizing the POIs into a structured *dataset* and uploading them to Google Maps: a simple gesture but one aimed at going beyond the technical requirements of the project and improving the digital readability of the municipalities, intervening on a concrete and easily activatable leverage point.

The third step was the critical synthesis of the evidence collected. Starting from interviews and mapping, the groups created files for each stakeholder, SWOT representations of each stakeholder's perspective on the territory, and an overall territorial SWOT that integrated what emerged from the POIs, in order to identify convergences, tensions, and opportunities. This work allowed

⁵ Point of Interest (POI): a georeferenced information unit representing a specific physical element in the territory. This category includes services, economic activities, public spaces, infrastructure, and elements of tangible and intangible heritage, regardless of their touristic interest.

groups to move beyond isolated observations to a strategic reading of the territory, still rooted in the voices and places encountered.

On this basis, the participants developed initial project hypotheses and identified areas where a *place-based* communication strategy could make a concrete contribution: connecting the resources that emerged with the right audiences, enhancing existing routes, services, and initiatives, and supporting the priorities shared with LAGs and administrations. Module B collected and developed these preliminary hypotheses into editorial plans and pilot content: the role of Module A was to provide, in a few days, the basic data, analyses, and ideas on which these strategies could be based.

This workshop setup also highlighted Liminal's approach: a Challenge adapted to the training context, which is not limited to transferring technical tools but uses a short, intensive, and structured cycle of fieldwork as a pedagogical device. The workshop was conceived as an acceleration of the relationship between theory and practice: the concepts introduced in the theoretical sessions are immediately put to the test through concrete and circumscribed objectives, generating two distinct moments of feedback. The first, more bottom-up, coincides with the uploading of POIs to Google Maps, which updates the digital readability of municipalities and offers an initial test bed to understand whether the work carried out meets real needs. The second, developed in Module B, consists of the public feedback of *place-based* communication strategies developed in dialogue with LAGs and administrations, to give shape and strength to projects and priorities that emerged during the analysis. In both cases, feedback is not just a "courtesy," but a fully-fledged learning phase: it allows us to verify the usefulness of the outputs, observe the reactions of local actors, gather new information, and feed it back into the learning cycle, fueling the continuous adjustment of theories, objectives, and working methods. The main methodological outcome of the workshop is precisely this: to propose a way of addressing the problems of fragile territories that combines theory and practice in rapid cycles of experimentation, in which each step of analysis is already designed to translate into a small but concrete step of transformation.

4.1

Schedule and Implementation

The workshop was structured as a coherent sequence of preparatory, operational, and reflective moments that allowed for an integrated transition from theory to practice. In line with the methodological approach described in the previous paragraph, after an introductory week online (October 6-13), consisting of four theoretical meetings organized by Rete Nazionale PAC - Rete LEADER, Prof. Caracci (GAL Elimos) and Liminal, participants acquired the conceptual foundations of local development, *place-based* communication, and the complexity of territorial contexts. Liminal, in

particular, led the session on October 10, dedicated to the presentation of its work, case studies, and territorial mapping and analysis methodologies that would form the core of Module A.

The in-person course began on October 25 in Marsala with institutional greetings and a presentation of the operational context. The first two and a half days (October 26–28 morning) were dedicated to Module A, led by Liminal. The first day revisited the theoretical framework of the territory as a complex system, presenting Liminal's *Challenge* methodology and translating it into an operational strategy for field activities. The participants, divided into four teams, co-designed the operational plan, defining the guiding questions for the semi-structured interviews, logistics, agenda, and mapping priorities based on their own territorial context of reference.

October 27 was devoted entirely to fieldwork in the four municipalities involved: Buseto Palizzolo, Misiliscemi, Valderice, and Vita. Each group, composed of about ten participants, was divided into subgroups. One group was dedicated to conducting interviews with local stakeholders (on average 10–11 per territory), selected from a preliminary list and enriched by additional contacts identified on site. The other was dedicated to mapping POIs, collecting all the metadata and photographs necessary to make them accessible via wayfinding platforms. The operational mapping and interview strategies were varied by the groups according to the morphological and social specificities of the territories, allowing for a diversified and comparable exploration.

On the morning of October 28, the groups met in Marsala for cross-analysis of the data and drafting of the territorial SWOT analysis, first from the point of view of the individual stakeholders and then overall from that of the group, formulating the first strategic hypotheses. That same afternoon, these were transferred to Module B, dedicated to translating strategies into communication actions: definition of personas, keywords, editorial plans, and production of pilot content (posts, reels, and strategic canvases). An interim public presentation on the 28th at midday facilitated the connection between the two modules and the validation of progress. The process concluded on October 30 in Altavilla Milicia with the public presentation of the results at the Forum LEADER 2025, during which each group illustrated its strategy and related communication plan.

Fig. 1
Schedule of training activities related to the Forum LEADER Giovani 2025.

Date	Location	Phase	Main Activities and Objectives
Oct. 6	Online	Introductory session	Presentation of the Forum LEADER Giovani 2025, overview of the program and training objectives by the National CAP Network - LEADER Network.
Oct. 8	Online	Introductory theory session (Prof. Caracci)	In-depth analysis of territorial marketing and <i>place-based</i> communication principles.
October 10	Online	Introductory theory session (Liminal)	Introduction to Liminal's work and case studies of past initiatives and methodologies developed.

Oct. 13	Online	Introductory theory session (CREA – National CAP Network - LEADER Network)	Introduction to CAP 2025-2029 policies and cooperation policies.
Oct. 25	Marsala	Opening	Arrival of participants, institutional greetings, and introduction to the workshop context.
Oct. 26	Marsala	Module A (Theory)	Provide the conceptual framework (complex systems, territorial fragility, leverage points) to give meaning to "what" would be done the following day.
Oct. 26	Marsala	Module A (Fieldwork preparation)	Prepare the fieldwork operationally, defining the guiding questions for the interviews, the operational plan, logistics, the agenda, and the division of the four work teams.
Oct. 27	Buseto Palizzolo, Misiliscemi, Valderice, Vita	Module A (Fieldwork)	The heart of the workshop. Collect data (POIs and interviews) to build "territorial legibility" and understand local dynamics.
Oct.	Marsala	Module A (Analysis)	Transform raw data into knowledge. Perform cross-checks and SWOT analysis to synthesize and give strategic meaning to the data collected. Develop a preliminary strategic project in which communication could be a central element.
Oct. 28	Marsala	Module B (Strategy)	Begin translating the analysis (SWOT) into action. Definition of <i>personas</i> , <i>keywords</i> , and editorial plans to give direction to communication strategies.
Oct.	Marsala	Module B (Production)	Create concrete outputs (posts, reels) and finalize strategic canvases. Transform strategy into ready-to-use content.
Oct. 30	Altavilla Milicia	Final presentation	Public presentation of projects, audience vote, evaluation by the Scientific Committee, and award ceremony for the winning group at the Forum LEADER 2025.

5.1

Training Outcomes

Participants acquired and tested key skills directly related to the methodological approach of the workshop. They learned how to structure territorial data (POI) and conduct semi-structured bilateral interviews, using SWOT analysis to transform heterogeneous information into a strategic

reading of the territory. They also experienced how to move from analysis to the formulation of a *place-based* communication strategy (defining personas, keywords, and editorial plans) and the production of digital content consistent with strategic objectives. The experience consolidated their ability to work intensively in multidisciplinary teams, managing the entire theoretical-practical-feedback cycle of Liminal's Challenge methodology within tight deadlines. The self-assessment of the course's learning outcomes was conducted on a scale from -2 ('strongly disagree') to +2 ('strongly agree'). Out of a total of 38 participants, 27 responded to the survey (71%). The results show overall effectiveness in all four aspects examined, with a particularly positive outcome on motivation to transform one's work into concrete projects. The applicability of what was learned is high (median 4/5, average 3.8): territorial analysis was the thematic area considered most useful and applicable, followed by communication.

Fig. 2

Summary table of self-assessments of training results.

Question	Average	Median
Following the workshop, I have a clearer understanding of how place-based data and practices can support my work	0.93	1.00 (Agree)
After the workshop, I feel more motivated to enhance what I already do in concrete projects.	1.19	1.00 (Agree)
After the workshop, I feel more confident about collaborating with colleagues and stakeholders.	1.04	1.00 (Agree)
After the workshop, I am better able to recognize opportunities and practical levers to activate what I have learned in the coming months.	0.74	1.00 (Agree)
To what extent is what you have learned applicable in your work/study/organization context?	3.81	4.0

Question	Category	Count
Which of the topics covered do you find most useful and applicable?	Territorial Analysis	23/27
	Communication	19/27
	Data Management	11/27
	Mapping	9/27
	Consultation	7/27

5.2

Project Outcomes

The teams produced a set of materials that can be used by the municipalities and GAL Elimos, in line with the objective of combining training and service to the territory. A key result is the documentation and uploading to Google Maps of 281 POIs, accompanied by photographs and the metadata necessary

for their use in wayfinding platforms: location, type, contacts, and brief text descriptions. For participants, mapping was a structured tool for exploring the territory independently, observing tourist, social, and infrastructural aspects that integrate and complement what emerged from the interviews. For the territories, the POIs are a concrete output: updating the information available online helps to increase digital readability, correct errors, and fill information gaps. Mapping was therefore not an academic exercise, but an operational contribution that acted on a strategic lever for the visibility and accessibility of local resources.

Added to these results are the outcomes of the module dedicated to communication: for each territory, a communication strategy was developed linked to a project identified during the field meetings, articulated in editorial plans, personas, keywords, and pilot content. These materials provide a basis for future actions by the LAG and the municipalities involved.

Among the four teams, the one assigned to the Municipality of Vita exemplifies the integration between the different phases of the workshop and the impact they can have on the territory. The group conducted more interviews than planned, using conversations with stakeholders to identify relevant themes, places, and projects, and maintaining constant coordination with the subgroup dedicated to mapping. This enabled not only the updating of existing POIs, but also to identify the largest number of new points of interest among all the teams, with a particular focus on votive shrines, which emerged in the interviews as a characteristic feature of the territory. On this basis, the group built a map of the votive shrines in the municipality of Vita, uploading them to Google Maps, and transformed it into a dedicated itinerary that emerged directly from dialogue with local actors. From the set of project proposals discussed, the team chose to focus its strategy on this theme, developing a coordinated package of visibility actions and the concept for the *visitvita.it* portal.

For these reasons, the group dedicated to the municipality of Vita was awarded the prize for best project: the municipality now has an information and narrative base that can be used immediately to promote its widespread heritage, and the team has clearly demonstrated how mapping, listening, analyzing, designing, and returning can translate into a concrete and implementable project outcome. In the case of the winning project, concrete implementation trajectories have been identified, thanks to the interest shown by local actors and the presence of operating conditions favorable to the experimentation of the proposed solutions.

Fig. 3

Summary table of the materials produced during the workshop by the four working groups.

Scope	Indicator	Value
Territory & data	Mapped POIs	281
	Municipalities covered	4
	Stakeholder interviews	41
Analysis and communication strategy	SWOT analyses	4
	Canvas completed	4
	Editorial plans	4
Production	Pilot content	28

Fig. 4

Representation of a point of interest mapped during activities at Vita (TP) and uploaded directly to Google Maps to make it easily discoverable by users.

5.3

Dissemination of the Results

The final presentation took place on October 30 in Altavilla Milicia, during the Forum LEADER Giovani 2025. Each group presented their territorial analysis, the strategies developed, and the content produced in the form of pitches developed in Module B to an audience of about 70 representatives of Italian LAGs. The session was divided into several parts: a public presentation of the projects, a public vote, and a technical evaluation, based on the votes and the judgment of the trainers responsible for Modules A and B and on the other hand of the judgment of a jury made up of members of the Scientific Committee not involved in the training activities. In both evaluations, the group dedicated to the Municipality of Vita prevailed and was proclaimed the winner of the workshop.

The presentation within the Forum represented not only the conclusion of the training course, but also an opportunity for direct discussion with those who work daily in local rural development: directors, technicians, and

administrators of the LAGs. In this way, the participants were able to present their results to an audience consistent with the content of the workshop, transforming the experience into an opportunity for visibility and the building of professional relationships, and strengthening the link between the Forum LEADER Giovani and the Forum LEADER as a common space for LAG operators and young participants interested in local development. Following the public presentation, bilateral meetings were organized with the municipal administrations involved, with the aim of sharing the results of the workshop.

Fig. 5

Slides presented during the final presentation of the work carried out at the Forum LEADER 2025.

6.1

Ex-post Evaluation

The evaluation approach adopted an adaptation of the Kirkpatrick model through an ex-post questionnaire and qualitative observations. The objective was to measure satisfaction, perceived learning, and the applicability of skills. The questionnaire was administered to 38 participants under the age of 35, from 17 regions of the country. Twenty-seven participants responded to the questionnaire, equal to 71% of the total. Feedback on the training outcomes is reported in section 5.1. Below are the results regarding satisfaction and the quality of the course.

Overall satisfaction is very high (4.3/5), as is the recommendation rate (4.6/5), indicating that participants perceived the workshop as useful and motivating. The relevance to their work or studies obtained an average of 3.8, confirming the good transferability of the skills learned. The workshop also encouraged the creation of professional networks, with an average of 14

new contacts per participant, considered useful for accelerating future projects (3.6/5).

From an educational point of view, the clarity of the objectives (3.5) and the usefulness of the materials (3.8) were rated positively, while facilitation (3.3) and logistics (3.1) showed room for improvement. The evaluation of working methods (3.9) confirmed the effectiveness of the collaborative and intensive approach. Finally, more than half of the participants (16 out of 25 responses) attribute a medium-high impact (over 50%) to the workshop on their vision, motivation, and ability to collaborate.

Overall, these results confirm the consistency between the methodological framework of the workshop and the objectives of the Forum LEADER Giovani. The high level of satisfaction and recommendation, combined with the perceived good transferability of skills, indicates that the intensive, Challenge-based format was recognized as useful and motivating. The combination of applied learning and professional networking also shows that the workshop functioned not only as a technical course, but also as a bridge between young people interested in local development and the LAG system, creating the conditions for what was learned to be translated into concrete initiatives in the various territories of origin.

Fig. 6

Summary table of the final questionnaire on overall satisfaction and quality of the course.

Question	Average	Median
Overall satisfaction	4.30/5	4.00/5
Relevance of the workshop to your work/studies in general	3.81/5	4.00/5
Would you recommend the experience to colleagues or friends?	4.59/5	5.00/5
How many useful connections, new contacts, or strengthened relationships did you make?	14	10
Can these connections accelerate activities in your context?	3.63/5	4.00/5
Clarity of objectives and deliverables	3.52/5	4.00/5
Usefulness of exercises and materials	3.85/5	4.00/5
Facilitation (timing/briefing/feedback)	3.30/5	3.00/6
Effectiveness of working methods in promoting active participation and discussion among participants	3.93/5	4.00/5
Logistics (Spaces/equipment/timing)	3.11/5	3.00/5
How much of the change (vision / motivation / collaboration / network) do you attribute to the workshop?	10-25	3/27
	25-50	6/27
	50-75	9/27
	75-90	7/27
	>90%	0/27

7.1 Lessons Learned and Recommendations

The workshop experience confirmed the effectiveness of the intensive format as a tool for learning in the field and serving local areas, capable of producing tangible results in a short time. The main value that emerged was cooperation: teamwork, sharing perspectives, and creating professional networks. From a methodological point of view, territorial analysis was indicated by many participants as the most useful and effective phase, confirming the central role of territorial legibility in the process. However, some logistical issues emerged, indicating the need for even more integrated planning between local partners, trainers, and organizers. It also emerged that, in order to exploit this potential, it will be important in the future to better balance theory and practice. Most of the theoretical content could be transferred online, freeing up time for reflection and discussion in the field.

Although the Forum LEADER Giovani 2025 retained some of the expectations and characteristics of previous editions, this edition placed greater emphasis on the idea of transforming each Forum into an opportunity for specialized learning. The program encouraged the participation of both new participants – interested not only in local development in general, but also in specific sub-topics that they are curious or passionate about – and young people already involved in past editions – who found continuity and further exploration. The methods tested also showed potential for transferability to cross-border territorial cooperation, in particular as a possible operational basis for future experiments within the Interreg Italy-Malta program.

While some editions in the past had already introduced a thematic focus, this year's main innovation was the desire to accompany the change in theme with a renewal of the methods transferred, bringing new, applicable, and replicable tools. In this way, the Forum is increasingly becoming a space in which each edition introduces not only a different theme, but also an updated set of methods, capable of evolving alongside training needs and territorial contexts. The Sicilian experience indicates that this direction is promising: a Forum LEADER Giovani that combines specialization and field testing can, over time, become both a gateway for new young people interested in local development and a recurring event to strengthen the community of practices that gravitates around the LAG network.